

HIGH RESOLUTION TIME DELAY ESTIMATION

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Abstract

A new method is presented for estimating the arrival times of deterministic signal pulses that are separated by less than the duration of the signal autocorrelation function. The method is based on the observation that if the signal has a flat band-limited spectrum, then the maximum-likelihood estimator for the signal time of arrivals can be approximately implemented as an unweighted least-squares exponential fitting problem. An improved linear prediction algorithm for high resolution exponential parameter estimation is then used to estimate the time of arrivals. The proposed method is tested via computer simulation and its performance is compared against the Cramer-Rao lower bound.

Introduction

Suppose we have a single sensor receiving a superposition of attenuated and delayed replicas of a known signal plus noise. From the received data we want to estimate the arrival times of the various replicas. For example, this type of problem occurs in radar and active sonar where the locations of scatterers or discontinuities in the medium are to be estimated from the back-scattered waveform. The locations of the scatterers or discontinuities can be estimated given the propagation speed and an estimate of the back-scattered pulse time of arrival. Mathematically, the received signal can be written as

$$y(t) = \sum_{k=1}^M a_k s(t - T_k) + n(t) \quad (1)$$

where $s(t)$ is the signal, the T_k are the signal time of arrivals, the a_k are the attenuations, and $n(t)$ is a noise component. In this paper we will assume that the noise waveform $n(t)$ is white gaussian with a two sided spectral density equal to $N_0/2$.

If the signal pulses are separated in time by an interval that is greater than the duration of the signal autocorrelation function, then the optimal estimator of the pulse time of arrival is the matched filter [1]. For non-white noise and delays greater than the duration of the signal autocorrelation function, the solution is given by Tremblay, et. al. [4]. The locations of the peaks in the matched filter output correspond to the arrival time [1]. This situation is not of interest here. We will consider the case when the signal pulses have a separation that is less than the duration of the signal autocorrelation function. This case is non-resolvable with matched filtering, hence alternate techniques must be sought.

For a review of some of the techniques used in the estimation of arrival times, the reader is referred to [1, 2, 3, 4]. Direct implementation of maximum likelihood is usually not practical for multiple pulses because the maximum likelihood estimator is a non-linear least squares problem which involves a high order search. In this paper a new method using an improved linear prediction method developed by Tufts and Kumaresan [5] will be presented. This algorithm was shown to have performance near the CRLB.

The new method is based on the observation that the maximum likelihood procedure can be transformed into a weighted least-squares exponential parameter estimation problem. The exponential parameter estimates then correspond to the maximum-likelihood estimate (MLE) of the pulse arrival times. If the pulse separation is less than the signal autocorrelation function duration, then the new method becomes a high resolution exponential parameter estimation problem.

The paper is organized as follows; In (I) derivation of the method, (II) computer simulation results, and finally, (III) a discussion and concluding remarks.

I. Derivation of an Approximate Solution of MLE Based on Linear Prediction

In the case of estimating parameters of a deterministic signal embedded in white gaussian noise, it is well known that one realization of the MLE is the least-squares estimator (Helstrom, pp 199, [8]). Using the model of the received data (formula (1)), the least-squares estimator corresponding to the MLE of the time of arrivals is by inspection

$$\min_{\hat{a}, \hat{\tau}} \int_0^T |Y(t) - \sum_{k=1}^M \hat{a}_k s(t - \hat{\tau}_k)|^2 dt \quad (2)$$

where \hat{a}_k and $\hat{\tau}_k$ correspond to the amplitudes and time of arrivals respectively that are to be estimated and T is the observation epoch. The pulse amplitudes a_k must also be estimated since they are assumed to non-random, but unknown.

The first step in the derivation is to re-express the integral in formula (2) in terms of the Fourier transforms of $y(t)$ and $s(t)$ using Parseval's theorem [7]. Applying Parseval's theorem [7] to formula (2) we get

$$\min_{\hat{a}, \hat{\tau}} \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |Y(w) - S(w) \sum_{k=1}^M \hat{a}_k e^{j\hat{\tau}_k w}|^2 dw \quad (3)$$

where $Y(w)$ and $S(w)$ are the Fourier transforms of $Y(t)$ and $S(t)$ respectively.

Assuming that $S(w)$ is non-zero, formula (3) can be re-written as a weighted least-squares estimator of the parameters of M complex exponentials as follows:

$$\min_{\hat{a}, \hat{\tau}} \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |S(w)|^2 \left| \frac{Y(w)}{S(w)} - \sum_{k=1}^M \hat{a}_k e^{j\hat{\tau}_k w} \right|^2 dw \quad (4)$$

where the term $|S(w)|$ can be interpreted as an error weighting function. From formula (4) it can be seen that the MLE can be implemented as the weighted least-squares fitting of M complex exponentials to the waveform $Y(w)/S(w)$. The above implementation of MLE (formula 4) is not very useful for arbitrary signal spectra. The author is not aware of any exponential parameter estimation algorithms (besides a multidimensional search) that can be easily adapted to handle the weighted error problem and provide good performance for arbitrary spectra.

However, consider a signal that has a flat band-limited spectrum, that is, the magnitude of the signal spectrum $|S(w)|$ can be approximated as follows:

$$|S(w)| \approx \begin{cases} B, & w_1 \leq |w| \leq w_2 \\ 0, & \text{elsewhere} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Then the minimization of formula (4) corresponds approximately to the standard least squares fitting of M complex exponentials to the waveform $Y(w)/S(w)$ over the interval $[w_1, w_2]$.

A brief outline of the proposed algorithm for signals with a flat band-limited spectrum is given below.

a) Form the discrete sequence $X_n = Y(w_1 + \Delta wn)/S(w_1 + \Delta wn)$, $n=0, 1, \dots, N-1$ such that $w_1 \leq w_1 + \Delta wn \leq w_2$. Δw is chosen at least to correspond to the Nyquist rate.

b) Then use an improved linear prediction algorithm developed by Tufts and Kumaresan [5] to estimate the M complex exponential parameters from the sequence X_n .

II. Computer Simulation Results

Computer simulation results for two sampled linear FM pulses (Linear FM pulses are commonly used in radar and sonar to obtain good range resolution) are presented and compared against the CRLB ([6], pp. 327). The sampled linear FM pulse that is used in the simulations is given by the formula (6)

$$s(n) = \sin[2\pi(6.2814 \times 10^{-5})(T_s n)^2], \quad n=0, 1, \dots, 199$$

where T_s , the sampling interval, is chosen to be 1 second. The log magnitude of the signal spectrum is shown in Fig. 1. It is shown that the computer simulation results compare favorably with the CRLB.

The received data vector we shall use is

$$y(n) = s(n-T_1) + s(n-T_2) + w(n) \quad (7)$$

for $n=0, 1, \dots, 199, 200, \dots, 199+T_2$

and where $s(n)$ is the signal given by formula (6), T_1 and T_2 are integer numbers corresponding to the time of arrivals in seconds and the $w(n)$ are independent, zero-mean computer generated Gaussian random variables with variance σ_w^2 .

The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is defined on a per signal pulse basis, this SNR is given as

$$\text{SNR} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{1}{2\sigma_w^2} \right) \quad (8)$$

where σ_w^2 is the variance of the noise samples in formula (7).

The time of arrival estimation algorithm is implemented in the steps outlined in Section I. For our computer simulation results we set SNR=20dB, $w_1 = -.02510\text{Hz}$, $w_2 = .2510\text{Hz}$, and $\Delta w = 1.731 \times 10^{-3} \text{Hz}$. This yielded a sequence of 30 samples. A predictor order of 22 was chosen, following a suggestion [5] that selecting a predictor order equal to $(3/4)N$ gives best performance.

The time of arrival T_1 is fixed at zero ($T_1 = 0$). The pulse separation T_2 was varied from 8 to 40 samples (the corresponding normalized separation in respect to the signal bandwidth B_w , $B_w T_2$ is from .20 to 1.00 where $B_w = .025 \text{Hz}$). These times of arrivals were chosen to correspond to the high resolution case. The signals are non-resolvable via matched filtering when $B_w T_2 < 1$.

In each simulation trial the data vector is computer generated using formulas (6-8). The performance of the algorithm was evaluated by measuring the expected value and mean-square error (MSE) of the estimated T_1 and T_2 over 50 independent simulation trials for each set of SNR and T_2 parameters.

The computer simulation results are compared against the CRLB for the time of arrivals assuming unknown signal amplitudes. The CRLB is calculated using the steps given in Whalen ([6], pp. 332) and then evaluated numerically. The simulation results and the CRLB for T_1 are tabulated in Table 1. The simulation results compare favorably to the CRLB. Also, the time of arrival estimates appear to be unbiased.

Although not presented here, additional computer simulations were performed at higher and lower SNR with similar results. For a normalized separation of .5, the threshold at which the measured MSE significantly exceeded the CRLB occurred at about SNR = -3dB.

III Conclusion

This method provides high resolution time of arrival estimates. For signals with a rectangular shaped spectrum, the proposed method provides good performance in terms of the estimation accuracy of the time of arrivals. It is noted that the algorithm can also be applied in the case of non-rectangular spectra. However, some degradation in estimation accuracy would be expected since the algorithm is no longer optimum in the sense of approximating MLE. An additional advantage of the proposed method is that it can handle an arbitrary number of signal pulses, however the number of pulses must be known.

References

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Fig. 1) Plot of the log magnitude of the signal (formula (6)) spectrum.

$B_W (T_2 - T_1)$	mean T_1	$\sqrt{\text{MSE } T_1}$	CRLB
1.00	-2.980×10^{-4}	3.407×10^{-3}	2.035×10^{-3}
.875	1.655×10^{-5}	3.447×10^{-3}	2.089×10^{-3}
.750	-7.731×10^{-4}	3.313×10^{-3}	2.274×10^{-3}
.625	6.057×10^{-4}	4.145×10^{-3}	2.650×10^{-3}
.500	2.333×10^{-3}	6.822×10^{-3}	3.285×10^{-3}
.425	6.120×10^{-5}	8.300×10^{-3}	3.854×10^{-3}
.350	-1.312×10^{-3}	1.232×10^{-3}	4.605×10^{-3}
.275	2.232×10^{-3}	1.958×10^{-3}	5.675×10^{-3}

Table 1) Estimation error of T_1 when SNR=20 dB based on 50 simulation trials. Note that all results are normalized in respect to the signal bandwidth B_W ($B_W = .025$ Hz). Below $B_W (T_2 - T_1) = .275$, the MSE significantly exceeds the CRLB.